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METONYMY, METAPHOR AND HOMONYMY IN STYLISTICS.

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ANNOTATION: This article is about approaches and will give a definition for stylistics, metonymy, metaphor, homonymy and their similarities and provide some examples. A metonymy is a word or phrase that is used to stand in for another word. Metaphors are a form of figurative language, which refers to words or expressions that mean something different from their literal definition. In the case of metaphors, the literal interpretation would often be pretty silly. For example, imagine what these metaphors would look like if you took them at face value: Love is a battlefield. Homonymy is recognized as a language universal. It creates lexical ambiguity in that a single form has two or more different meanings. For example: 1.ball, n - a sphere, any spherical body. 2.ball, n, a large dancing party.

KEY WORDS: Stylistics, metonymy, metaphor, homonymy, homophones and homograph.

Stylistics, a branch of applied linguistics, is the study and interpretation of texts of all types and/or spoken language in regard to their linguistic and tonal style, where style is the particular variety of language used by different individuals and/or in different situations or settings. Stylistic devices can also be called figures of speech because they often involve non-literal or figurative language. There are various types of stylistic devices. The following subheadings provide stylistic device examples for the most well-known types.

METONYMY.

Metonymy is a figure of speech in which thing or concept is called by its own name but rather by the name of something associated with meaning with that thing or concept.

The word "Metonymy" and "Metonymy" are come from the Greek: metonymia "a change of name", from meta "after, beyond"- onymia, a suffix used to name figure of speech, from "name". For instance, "Hollywood" is used to as a metonym for the U.S. film industry because of the fame and cultural identity of Hollywood, a district of the city of Los Angeles, California, as the historical center of the film studios and

film stars. Metonymy and related figures of speech are common in every talk and writing. Polysemy, multiple meanings of a single word or phrase, sometimes result from relations of metonymy. Both metonymy and metaphor involve the substitution of one term for another. In metaphor, this substitution is based on some specific analogy between two things, whereas in metonymy the substitution is based on some understood association or contiguity. Metonymy is closely related to synecdoche, the naming of a part for the whole or a whole for the part, and is a common poetic device. Metonymy has the effect of creating concrete and vivid images in place of generalities, as in the substitution of a specific "grave" for the abstraction "death." Metonymy is standard journalistic and headline practice as in the use of "city hall" to mean "municipal government" and of the "White House" to mean the "president of the United States." "The pen is mightier than the sword." The words – 'pen' and 'sword' contribute to the effect of metonymy. The two words are not used in a literal sense. On the contrary, the term 'pen' refers to written words and the term 'sword' refers to military aggression.

- My class teacher asked me to give her a hand with the notebooks and records.
- All of us were happy that Natalie finally made it to Hollywood.
- Everyone should pledge their allegiance to the crown.

METAPHOR.

A metaphor is a figure of speech that describes an object or action in a way that isn't literally true, but helps explain an idea or make a comparison

Here are the basics:

- A metaphor states that one thing is another thing
- It equates those two things not because they actually are the same, but for the sake of comparison or symbolism
- If you take a metaphor literally, it will probably sound very strange (are there actually any sheep, black or otherwise, in your family?)
- Metaphors are used in poetry, literature, and anytime someone wants to add some color to their language.

A word or phrase for one thing that is used to refer to another thing in order to show or suggest that they are similar. An object, activity, or idea that is used as a symbol of something else. Metaphors show up in literature, poetry, music, and writing, but also in speech. If we hear someone say "metaphorically speaking," it probably means that you shouldn't take what they said as the truth, but as more of an idea. For example, it's finals period and after exams, students are saying things like "That test was murder." It's a fair guess they're still alive if they're making comments

about the test, so this is an example of speaking metaphorically or figuratively. Metaphors can make your words come to life, and often, you can use a metaphor to make your subject more relatable to the reader or to make a complex thought easier to understand. They can also be a tremendous help when you want to enhance your writing with imagery. As a common figure of speech, metaphors turn up everywhere from novels and films to presidential speeches and even popular songs. When they're especially good, they're hard to miss. For example: All the world's a stage, and all the men and women merely players. They have their exits and their entrances.(William Shakespeare)

HOMONYMY.

In linguistics, homonyms are words which are either homographs—words that have the same spelling (regardless of pronunciation)—or homophones—words that have the same pronunciation (regardless of spelling)—or both. The word 'homonym' comes from the Greek word 'homonymos' which means 'having the same name'. The prefix 'homo' means the same, and the suffix 'nym' means name. Homonyms are two or more words with the same spelling or pronunciation, but with different meanings. For example: 1. bank, n - a shore. 2. bank, n - an institution for receiving, lending, exchanging and safeguarding money.

Homonyms - the words of one and the Same language which are identical phonetically or graphically in all or several grammar forms but which have essential difference in lexical and grammatical meanings. For example: 1. A penny is one cent. 2. A soap has a nice scent. 3. She sent me a letter. 1. The bridge is made of steel. 2. Do not steal. Homonyms are words that have different meanings but are pronounced or spelled the same way. There are two types of homonyms: homophones and homographs. Homophones sound the same but are often spelled differently. Each of two or more words having the same pronunciation but different meanings, origins, or spelling, for example new and knew. Each of two or more words spelled the same but not necessarily pronounced the same and having different meanings and origins. For example, bass (the fish, rhymes with class) and bass (the instrument, rhymes with ace) are homographs.

In conclusion: Using a metonymy serves as a double purpose - it breaks up any awkwardness of repeating the same phrase over and over and it changes the wording to make the sentences more interesting. In addition to its use in everyday speech, metonymy is a figure of speech in some poetry and in much rhetoric. Greek and Latin scholars of rhetoric made significant contributions to the study of metonymy. We can use metaphor for allows us to visualize complex ideas in new ways. Creative a vivid,

original description of people, places and events. Forces readers think and interpret for themselves. Homonyms can be more confusing for young readers or people learning English as a second language, usually because they are not yet familiar with alternate definitions of the word.

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